

IN SITU METROLOGY FOR DEGRADATION STUDIES OF PEROVSKITE SOLAR CELLS

George Koutsourakis^{1*}, Yameng Cao¹, Bowei Li², K. D. G. Imalka Jayawardena², R. M. Indrachapa Bandara², Sebastian Wood¹, James C. Blakesley¹, W. Zhang, S. Ravi P. Silva² and Fernando A. Castro^{1,2}

¹National Physical Laboratory (NPL), Hampton Road, Teddington, Middlesex, TW11 0LW, United Kingdom, UK

²Advanced Technology Institute, University of Surrey, Guildford, Surrey GU2 7XH, UK

ABSTRACT: Perovskite solar cells (PSC) have attracted considerable attention in recent years due to the high efficiencies achieved, their scalability potential and the introduction of record efficiency tandem devices with a perovskite layer on top of silicon. Although the reported efficiencies and scalability approaches demonstrated show great potential for this technology, stability issues are a significant obstacle for PSC before they can compete with established PV technologies. Although efficient encapsulation offers some protection from environmental factors, encapsulation will never be perfect and through the years some permeation of oxygen and humidity into PV modules is inevitable. There are a number of critical factors for PSC degradation, and tests require accurate conditions and measurements in order to distinguish different degradation mechanisms. *In situ* metrology for ageing tests of perovskite PV devices has been developed at NPL that involves accurately controlled environments that can simulate realistic encapsulation conditions, while applying electrical measurements and spatial characterisation techniques. Environmental conditions including atmospheric composition, spectrum and intensity of illumination, and temperature can be accurately controlled. At the same time, current-voltage measurements, luminescence imaging, and photocurrent mapping of PSC can be performed during degradation. This allows the collection of a significant amount of data, in order to record the failure processes of samples and reveal the degradation mechanisms.

Keywords: Perovskite, Degradation, Characterisation

1 INTRODUCTION

Perovskite solar cells (PSC) have demonstrated high efficiencies in recent years [1], with potential for scalability and low processing costs compared to conventional established photovoltaic (PV) devices [2]. The realisation of tandem devices with a top perovskite layer and a bottom silicon cell has led to new records for power conversion efficiency [3][4]. Although high efficiencies and scalability routes show great potential for this technology, stability issues are a still a barrier for PSC before they can compete with established PV technologies. Even with the best available encapsulation, some amount of moisture and oxygen will eventually penetrate inside a PV module throughout its warranted lifetime of 20 years [5]. This highlights that bankability of future perovskite products will strongly depend on resolving reliability issues.

Several studies have been reported in the literature, investigating the critical factors for PSC degradation. PSC devices demonstrate different degradation rates and mechanisms depending on electrical bias during degradation [6], temperature and illumination levels [7], spectral profile of illumination [8], humidity [9] or oxygen content [10] in the given atmosphere. Considering the plurality of factors that affect degradation rates, several environmental and electrical parameters have to be monitored and controlled for a reliable assessment. Current-voltage (I-V) curve features such as hysteresis increase the complexity of such tests and require consistent approaches in order to allow meaningful interpretation of measurements. Ambient temperature and irradiance operating conditions can have a minor effect on the degradation of PSC devices even in perfect encapsulation conditions [11]. Nevertheless, some amounts of oxygen and humidity will inevitably penetrate inside devices in real operating conditions and may significantly accelerate degradation.

In this work, *in-situ* metrology methodologies for degradation studies of perovskite PV devices are presented that have been developed at NPL. These involve

accelerated tests in controlled environments with the capability to apply spatial characterisation techniques and electrical measurements during such ageing tests. Portable environmental chambers have been developed in-house at NPL. These are combined with an accurate gas mixing system, in order to achieve precise control of temperature, oxygen and humidity levels, while providing electrical contacting and optical access to samples. An LED-based light source is used for illumination of samples during ageing experiments. In addition, an optical measurement system has been developed, capable of performing *in situ* photoluminescence (PL) and electroluminescence (EL) imaging as well as fast current mapping of samples, from within the environmental chamber's optical window. This allows electrical and imaging measurements to be acquired during degradation tests, linking performance changes with spatially resolved features that develop during degradation. Different aspects of spatial and electrical performance of samples during ageing tests can be monitored and distinguished, such as local collection efficiency, electrical contact failures and material degradation.

Such degradation tests, in accurately controlled environments, can help simulate realistic encapsulation conditions, where some permeation of oxygen and humidity is inevitable. A better understanding of the degradation mechanisms of PSC under specific environmental conditions can be gained through such tests. This can contribute towards the development of more stable perovskite PV devices, further development of defect engineering methods [12] leading to more stable devices and as a result a faster development of commercial products based on perovskite materials.

Through the metrology methodologies developed in this work, the encapsulation requirements can be defined, also providing guidelines towards replicating realistic encapsulation conditions in accelerated ageing tests. Moreover, the requirements for material stability for PSC based devices can be drawn, in order to achieve reliability at realistic encapsulation conditions

3 MEASUREMENT SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

3.1 Chambers and gas control system

Two types of portable environmental chambers have been developed in-house at NPL. The smaller chambers presented on the left of Figure 1 can accept up to 2 samples of 2 cm × 2 cm each. The samples can be optically accessed by glass windows, for illumination or optical measurements. The large chamber type presented on the right of Figure 1 can accept up to 6 samples of 3 cm × 3 cm each, where both sides can be accessed by large optical windows. Temperature control provided by a glass/ITO heating plate is integrated into the chamber, while contactless phosphor thermometry methods have also been explored for accurate temperature feedback of samples [13]. Both chambers have reconfigurable electrical probes for contacting samples of any contacting scheme or architecture. The chambers can also be used to transfer samples between labs and measurement systems, while keeping samples in a controlled environment.

Figure 1: Pictures of the two environmental chambers developed at NPL.

The gas mixing control system consists of 3 channels that can accept different gases to create specific environmental conditions in the chamber under use. The gas control and feedback system allows an oxygen level range of ~ 0% (< 0.5 ppm) to 21 % and a humidity range of ~ 0% (< 1 ppm) up to 10 % R.H.. The oxygen leak rate during transport (when not connected to a constant gas flow line) is less than 1 ppm per hour. Oxygen and humidity measurements have been calibrated and are traceable up to a relative uncertainty of ± 10 % for oxygen and 20 % for humidity values.

3.2 Electrical characterisation and imaging measurements

The ageing and measurement acquisition system for *in situ* characterisation of PSC samples is presented in Figure 2. Internal adjustable chamber probes can provide contacting of multiple samples per slot, for the cases when substrates consist of multiple cells. All samples can be accessed consecutively for electrical measurements via a switching system. The LED array for illumination during ageing tests consists of red, green, blue and UV LEDs, each can be individually controlled in order to set a specific spectrum profile. IR LEDs were excluded to avoid unwanted radiative heating of samples. The light output qualifies as class ABA for spectrum, uniformity, and stability, respectively, according to IEC 60904-7:2007 for the spectral range of < 700 nm only.

The *in situ* measurement system can provide I-V curves of samples during degradation, as well as current mapping measurements, PL and EL imaging from within the chamber. Current mapping is realised using a 658 nm fibre coupled laser source, the scan is implemented by a

Digital Micromirror Device (DMD) [14] integrated into an optical system, at a maximum sampling rate of 30 points/s [15]. PL and EL imaging is realised with a CMOS camera using a 720 nm longpass filter to reject the LED illumination in the case of PL imaging, but allow the luminescence emission of the PSC samples. Apart from the LED array, PL excitation can also be achieved using the laser source and the DMD system. This option has the advantage of selecting only the areas of interest for excitation, avoiding saturation of the camera from high intensity areas of the substrate outside the defined sample areas.

Figure 2: Schematic of the measurement system for *in situ* spatial characterisation of PSC during ageing tests.

An additional capability of the system can capture PL images of samples during I-V sweeps, providing a PL image for every point on the I-V curve. This voltage dependent PL imaging process can be implemented during ageing tests, providing useful links between local defects and performance non-uniformities with I-V curves.

4 IN SITU CHARACTERISATION RESULTS

Figure 3 shows from left to right, PL imaging, EL imaging and photocurrent mapping results of a glass/ITO/SnO₂/Cs_{0.05}FA_{0.80}MA_{0.05}Pb(I_{0.85}Br_{0.15})₃/spiro/Au/glass structure sample prepared using chlorobenzene as the anti-solvent. [16]. It can be observed that each spatial characterisation technique reveals different features of the sample. Some defects appear in all images, while most of the features only appear when using a specific imaging method. The large circular feature on the right side of the sample clearly visible in the PL image and marginally visible in the EL image is a real feature and not an artefact of the optical system. Nevertheless, it does not appear in the current map, demonstrating that it does not affect local performance of the sample. In general terms, PL imaging monitors material quality during ageing experiments, whereas EL imaging monitors mostly contact quality and is affected by local series resistance. Photocurrent mapping reveals spatial collection efficiency and local photocurrent generation for the device. Some weak interference visible in the current map is due to dust particles in the optical system creating diffraction of the collimated beam, not a feature of the sample. Using such techniques during ageing experiments, the development of defects during degradation can be monitored. Failure mechanisms can be assigned to specific failure modes, such as material degradation, contact failure, shunting, etc..

An I-V curve of a different PSC sample (~0.25 cm² of each cells with the structure of Glass/ITO/Poly-TPD/perovskite/PCBM/BCP/Ag is presented in Figure 4.

Figure 3. From left to right: PL imaging, EL imaging and current mapping of the same PSC sample from within the chamber and using the measurement system presented in this work.

In the same figure, PL images captured at different points of the IV curve are presented, their capture positions are marked on the I-V curve with blue dots. At I_{SC} , the PL intensity of the cell area is low (lower than the background outside the area of the sample) and fairly uniform across the cell. This is expected since charge carriers are efficiently collected before they radiatively recombine.

Figure 4. I-V curve of a PSC sample and PL images captured at the points marked with blue dots. All PL images have the same scaling.

A higher PL signal is observed from the area on the right outside the cell, where the cell's highly reflective back contact extends and generated charge carriers are not collected. At the maximum power the PL image is similar to that observed at I_{SC} , with some marginally visible areas providing some weak PL signal, indicating insufficient collection. At the V_{OC} point, the material quality can be evaluated, as this will resemble the non-contacted PL imaging. Nevertheless, since the device is still contacted, local voltage differences can still be present. At forward bias (1.2 V selected here), contact performance and series resistance are dominant effects so PL imaging resembles a superposition of EL imaging with the PL image as the

background.

The performance of the PSC sample is monitored during ageing tests, in order to determine specific failure modes for given accelerated ageing conditions. This also helps to monitor the behaviour of specific defects as it will be shown in the ageing example for this sample in the next section.

5 AGEING TESTS

As an example of electrical and optical monitoring during degradation, the above PSC sample was kept under constant illumination of 700 W/m^2 , using the LED array system, with a sample temperature of $35 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Using the gas mixing system, the sample was initially kept for 50 hours in a dry N_2 atmosphere with 1 % of O_2 , then exposed to an additional 50 hours with 5 % O_2 and finally, exposed to dry synthetic air (21 % O_2). The I-V curves at the above specific intervals, along with the initial one, are presented in Figure 5.

Figure 5. I-V curve of a PSC sample and PL images captured at the points marked with blue dots. All PL images have the same scaling.

It can be seen that over the first 50 hours in the 1 % O_2 atmosphere degradation is minor and it is mainly driven by loss of current, while voltage is almost unchanged, showing a marginal increase. Similarly, for another 50 hours of 5 % O_2 , there is an additional loss of current but no decrease in voltage. When atmospheric levels of O_2 are introduced by inserting synthetic dry air into the chamber, performance declines faster. After the additional 60 hours in dry air, the sample has lost 33 % of its I_{SC} but there is no V_{OC} change. Nevertheless, Efficiency has been reduced from a maximum of 15.7 % to 8.8 %, with the degradation rate clearly depending on the amount of oxygen present in

the chamber as it can be observed in Figure 6.

As it can be observed in the above results, after an initial preconditioning phase, degradation already starts with conditions of 1 % O₂ in dry atmosphere. It has to be noted that even 1 % O₂ levels are rather high oxygen levels, simulating poor encapsulation conditions of current PV module technology. Nevertheless, real operating conditions will also include permeation of an amount of humidity within the encapsulation and higher operating temperatures, factors that are not included in the results presented in this work. The combination of all of the above factors can potentially activate multiple degradation mechanisms that will accelerate degradation rates of PSC in realistic conditions.

Figure 6. Degradation of the efficiency with varying oxygen concentration levels within the chamber.

In Figure 7 PL images of the sample at V_{oc} conditions, within the environmental chamber during degradation are presented. In the initial state presented at the top of the figure, it can be observed that the device area is mostly uniform, with a number of local defects of low PL signal visible. After 50 hours at 1 % O₂ and 50 hours at 5 % O₂ more high PL signal local defects can be observed, with some of the ones that previously appeared dark now appearing bright. The zoomed-in area is a typical example of this behaviour, where a local defect that appeared dark initially starts appearing bright from its centre. At the final state almost all of the local defects have a high PL signal that stays constant regardless of voltage changes (from I_{sc} to V_{oc}). Nevertheless, EL imaging shows that all defects (bright or dark) do not provide any EL emission. This shows that these defects have developed local contacting problems, since they no longer respond to changes in voltage applied to the device and are responsible for the losses of current at the final degraded state.

The above results demonstrate an example of the usefulness of spatial characterisation techniques during degradation tests, simultaneously with electrical performance measurements. The spatial characteristics of specific failure mechanisms when simulating encapsulation conditions can be studied during degradation. Considering the amount of data that is acquired during the above tests and the large number of environmental conditions being monitored, additional data management and data processing tools from the data science field can prove useful for faster and more efficient analysis of results.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In situ metrology systems for ageing tests of PSC devices have been developed at NPL and are presented in this work. These include portable, in-house developed environmental chambers, accurate and traceable gas control system and temperature and irradiance control equipment. The aim is to be able to simulate realistic

encapsulation conditions and perform ageing tests under such conditions. In addition, *in situ* electrical measurements and spatial characterisation techniques such as luminescence imaging and current mapping can be applied during ageing tests.

Figure 7. PL imaging of the sample under V_{oc} conditions, within the environmental chamber. From top to bottom; initial state; after 50 hours at 1 % O₂ and 50 hours at 5 % O₂; after an additional 60 hours of 21 % O₂; EL imaging at the final state at 1.1 V.

The measurement examples in this work demonstrate the utility of such tools for the investigation of degradation mechanisms of PSC and their significance towards improving the reliability of this technology. The temporal, spatial and electrical characteristics of defects can be studied and associated with specific environmental conditions. These capabilities will contribute towards determining the realistic requirements for the stability of perovskite materials within realistic encapsulation conditions.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work is funded by the CORNET project, under the European Union's HORIZON 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 760949.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. Chen and N. G. Park, "Inorganic Hole Transporting Materials for Stable and High Efficiency Perovskite Solar Cells," *J. Phys. Chem. C*, vol. 122, no. 25, pp. 14039–14063, 2018.
- [2] F. Matteocci *et al.*, "High efficiency photovoltaic module based on mesoscopic organometal halide perovskite," *Prog. Photovoltaics Res. Appl.*, vol. 24, no. 4, pp. 436–445, Apr. 2016.
- [3] K. A. Bush *et al.*, "23.6%-efficient monolithic perovskite/silicon tandem solar cells with improved stability," *Nat. Energy*, vol. 2, no. 4, 2017.
- [4] OxfordPV, "Oxford PV perovskite solar cell achieves 28% efficiency," 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://www.oxfordpv.com/news/oxford-pv-perovskite-solar-cell-achieves-28-efficiency>. [Accessed: 03-Jan-2019].
- [5] M. D. Kempe, A. A. Dameron, and M. O. Reese, "Evaluation of moisture ingress from the perimeter of photovoltaic modules," *Prog. Photovoltaics Res. Appl.*, vol. 22, no. 11, pp. 1159–1171, Nov. 2014.
- [6] K. Domanski, E. A. Alharbi, A. Hagfeldt, M. Grätzel, and W. Tress, "Systematic investigation of the impact of operation conditions on the degradation behaviour of perovskite solar cells," *Nat. Energy*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 61–67, 2018.
- [7] T. Duong *et al.*, "Light and elevated temperature induced degradation (LeTID) in perovskite solar cells and development of stable semi-transparent cells," *Sol. Energy Mater. Sol. Cells*, vol. 188, no. August, pp. 27–36, 2018.
- [8] S.-W. Lee *et al.*, "UV Degradation and Recovery of Perovskite Solar Cells," *Sci. Rep.*, vol. 6, no. 1, p. 38150, Dec. 2016.
- [9] J. Yang, B. D. Siempelkamp, D. Liu, and T. L. Kelly, "Investigation of CH₃NH₃PbI₃ Degradation Rates and Mechanisms in Controlled Humidity Environments Using in Situ Techniques," *ACS Nano*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 1955–1963, Feb. 2015.
- [10] A. Senocrate *et al.*, "Interaction of oxygen with halide perovskites," *J. Mater. Chem. A*, vol. 6, no. 23, pp. 10847–10855, 2018.
- [11] W. Tress *et al.*, "Performance of perovskite solar cells under simulated temperature-illumination real-world operating conditions," *Nat. Energy*, vol. 4, no. July, 2019.
- [12] B. Li, V. Ferguson, S. R. P. Silva, and W. Zhang, "Defect Engineering toward Highly Efficient and Stable Perovskite Solar Cells," *Adv. Mater. Interfaces*, vol. 5, no. 22, p. 1800326, Nov. 2018.
- [13] Y. Cao *et al.*, "In situ contactless thermal characterisation and imaging of encapsulated photovoltaic devices using phosphor thermometry," *Prog. Photovoltaics Res. Appl.*, no. February, p. pip.3142, Jun. 2019.
- [14] L. J. Hornbeck, "The DMD™ Projection Display Chip: A MEMS-Based Technology," *MRS Bull.*, vol. 26, no. 4, pp. 325–327, Apr. 2001.
- [15] F. Bausi, G. Koutsourakis, J. C. Blakesley, and F. A. Castro, "High-speed digital light source photocurrent mapping system," *Meas. Sci. Technol.*, vol. 30, no. 9, p. 095902, Sep. 2019.
- [16] R. M. I. Bandara *et al.*, "Tin(IV) dopant removal through anti-solvent engineering enabling tin based perovskite solar cells with high charge carrier mobilities," *J. Mater. Chem. C*, vol. 7, no. 27, pp. 8389–8397, 2019.